

Non-Ionic Pt(II) Complexes of Uni- and *Bis* γ -Carbon Bonded Acetylacetonato Ligand

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On reacting $\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})_2$ with 3- and 4-picoline at 110° , four non-ionic Pt(II) complexes containing uni- and *bis* γ -carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand have been isolated. On the basis of chemical analysis, infrared and ^1H nmr spectral evidence, these complexes have been characterised as $[\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{L}]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})_2\text{L}_2]$ where L is 3 or 4-picoline.

CCOORDINATION of γ -carbon atom of the acetylacetonato ligand to the metal was first reported by Hazzel *et al*¹. Mason *et al*² also reported that the Werner's compound was in fact $\text{K}[\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{Cl}]^3$. Since then several kinds of $\gamma\text{-ac.ac}$ complexes⁴ have been reported. Also complexes of the type $[(\text{ac.ac})\text{Cl.Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{M}(\text{II})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{Pt.Cl}(\text{ac.ac})]$, where M(II) stands for divalent metal ions, have been well studied^{5,6}. But non-ionic Pt(II) complexes containing uni- and *bis* γ -carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand were reported for the first time by Yamamoto *et al*^{7,8}. Such complexes have also been reported^{9,10} with Pd(II) where they contain only uni- γ -carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand. Reactions of central and terminal carbon bonded Pd(II) complexes with substitution labile complexes were studied in this laboratory and the results have been communicated^{11,12}. Reactivity of γ -carbon bonded acetylacetonato moiety in $[\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})(\text{py})]$ was being studied¹³ by us when reaction of $\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})_2$ with several other Lewis bases was investigated. As a result, two complexes of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{L}]$ and $[\text{Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})_2\text{L}_2]$, where L is a nitrogen base like 3 or 4-methyl pyridine, have been isolated and characterised and are reported here.

Experimental

$\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})_2$ (0.75 g) was suspended in 4-picoline (5 ml) in a stoppered vessel and stirred at 110°

for 2 hrs when a deep brown solution was obtained. The solution was cooled in a refrigerator for 30 minutes and 30 ml of *n*-hexane was added. The mixture was kept in a refrigerator overnight when a white crystalline compound precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with hexane and dried in vacuum. The compound was extracted with ether (50 ml) and the precipitate filtered. The precipitate was identified to be the *bis*- γ -carbon bonded complex. The filtrate was concentrated to 10 ml and hexane (20 ml) was added to precipitate the complex-containing uni- γ -carbon bonded compound. Compounds were prepared in a similar way with 3-picoline.

Ir spectra were recorded in Nujol mulls using Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621 spectrometers. ^1H nmr spectra of the γ -picoline compound was measured in CDCl_3 solution with tetramethyl silane as internal reference using 100 Mz Japan electron optics spectrometer. Molecular weight was determined by J. Gohda of Osaka City University, with a Knauer vapour phase osmometer, in CHCl_3 medium at 25° . Analytical and ir spectral data are listed in Table 1 and ^1H nmr data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

From the elemental analysis and infrared spectra the two types of compounds are classified as $[\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})\text{L}](\text{A})$ and $[\text{Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})_2\text{L}_2](\text{B})$ complexes. These compounds are monobasic on

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF COMPLEXES

Compound	C	H	N	$\gamma\text{-ac.ac}$	ac.ac	$\nu(\text{Pt}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{Pt}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{Pt}-\text{N})$
$\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})$	39.25	4.18	2.75	1698	1565	460	575	330
$(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})$	(39.50)	(4.32)	(2.88)	1660	1550			
($\gamma\text{-pic}$)					1530			
$\text{Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})_2$	45.42	4.71	4.73	1660	—	—	570	335
($\gamma\text{-pic}$) ₂	(45.58)	(4.83)	(4.84)	1610				
$\text{Pt}(\text{ac.ac})$	39.32	4.21	2.69	1695	1565	450	578	330
($\gamma\text{-ac.ac}$)	(39.50)	(4.32)	(2.88)	1655	1550			
($\beta\text{-pic}$)					1525			
$\text{Pt}(\gamma\text{-ac.ac})$	45.40	4.74	4.71	1660	—	—	573	325
($\beta\text{-pic}$) ₂	(45.58)	(4.83)	(4.84)	1610				

The calculated values are in the parentheses.

$\gamma\text{-pic}$ = 4-methyl pyridine,

$\beta\text{-pic}$ = 3-methyl pyridine.

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TABLE 2—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA δ (ppm)

Compound	δ (ppm)	Assignments	J/Hz
A. Pt(ac.ac)(γ-ac.ac) (γ-pic)	1.82 s	CH ₃ of ac.ac	J(Pt-H)=132
	1.95 s		
	5.45 ss	CH of ac.ac	
	2.20 ss	CH ₂ of γ-ac.ac	
	5.0	CH of γ-ac.ac	
	2.44	CH ₂ of γ-pic	
	8.62, 8.68	CH of γ-pic	
B. Pt(γ-ac.ac) ₂ (γ-pic) ₂	1.84 ss	CH ₃ of γ-ac.ac	J(Pt-H)=105
	4.5 ss	CH of γ-ac.ac	
	2.4	CH ₂ of γ-pic	
	8.5, 8.6	CH ₂ of γ-pic	
	7.3, 7.4		

s=singlet, ss=singlet with satellite.

the basis of the observed and calculated molecular weight data of the γ-picoline complex i.e., [Pt(ac.ac)(γ-ac.ac)(γ-pic)]. Mol. wt. obsd. 465 calcd. 486, [Pt(ac.ac)₂(γ-pic)₂]. Mol. wt. obsd. 560, calcd. 579. Spectrum of compound (A) is very similar to that reported for K[Pt.Cl(ac.ac)(γ-ac.ac)]⁶. Bands in the 1600-1700 cm⁻¹ region are assigned to ketonic γ-carbon bonded ac.ac molecule and bands in the 1500-1600 cm⁻¹ region are attributed to the O, O'-chelating ac.ac ligand. In addition to this, another band is observed ~1615 cm⁻¹ assigned to the ring vibration of coordinated picoline molecule. Two bands due to γ-ac.ac ligand in (A) appeared at a higher wave number by 15-20 cm⁻¹ than in the palladium analogue⁹. Absence of bands in the 1500-1600 cm⁻¹ region in case of (B) indicated the absence of O-bonded chelate. Two bands at 1660 and 1610 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to ν(C=O) of the carbon bonded γ-ac.ac ligand by comparing them with reported values of 1652 and 1626 cm⁻¹ of Na₂[Pt.Cl(γ-ac.ac)₂]⁶. In addition to it in (A) ν(Pt-O) and ν(Pt-C) appear at 460 and 575 cm⁻¹ and in compound (B) only ν(Pt-C) appears at 570 cm⁻¹ which confirms the formulation of the complexes. ν(Pt-N) in the complexes appear at 330-335 cm⁻¹ region.

The ¹H nmr parameters of complexes are listed in Table 2. Assignment of the signals have been made by comparing them with those reported for similar complexes^{4,7-10}. Two methyl groups in the O, O'-chelated ac.ac in (A) appear as non-equivalent and give signals at 1.82 and 1.95 ppm. Methine signal appears at 5.45 ppm. The methyl and methine signal of γ-ac.ac ligand are observed at

2.20 and 5.00 ppm with satellites due to coupling with 195 Pt nucleus. Methine proton of γ-ac.ac ligand in complex (A) resonates at a lower field than that in (B) and also in comparison with the compound Pt(ac.ac)(γ-ac.ac)(PPh₃)(4.04 ppm) by almost 1 ppm. These methine proton signals are accompanied by satellite bands due to 195 Pt with a larger coupling constant for (A) than for (B). Such a difference was observed in the case of a similar compound⁸. In addition to this, CH₃ and CH signals of bonded γ-picoline appear (Table 2) which are different from the signals of free γ-picoline. In the compound (B), only one methyl and one methine signals are observed at 1.84 and 4.50 ppm (with satellites) attributed to the CH₃ and CH proton signals respectively of the γ-ac.ac ligand. CH₂ group of γ-picoline gives signals at 2.4 ppm and CH proton signals are observed around 7.3 to 8.6 ppm region.

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